

Consent Form

Principal Investigator: Marie-Therese Mäder, Università die Macerata

In this form you are consenting to participate in the research study:

Promising Images of Love

The Mediatisation of Values and Norms in Religious and Secular Wedding Narratives.

Informed consent form, if the data subject is an adult

I, the undersigned , declare as follows:

- I have received a copy of the *Participant Information Sheet* (PIS) that explains the use of my data in this research. I understand its contents and agree to the collection and use of my data for this research.
- I am voluntarily taking part in this project.
- I do not expect to receive any benefit or payment for my participation;
- I authorize the University of Macerata to process my personal data;
- I have been able to ask any questions I might have, and I understand that I am free to contact the researcher with any questions I may have in the future.
- I confirm that I have been informed of my right of access to any personal data related to me, a right to correct, and a right to oppose the processing of personal data relating to me for direct marketing purposes. I can also withdraw my consent for the future at any time without any justification.
- I will not have any rights to any commercial benefits that result from this research. I also agree that I will not derive any monetary or other benefits from this research.

Place and date _____

Signature for granted consent _____